
Research

Chinese foreign policy and its impact on Africa

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Abstract: Today, the African region receives much more attention among scholars than a few years ago. Africa remains one of the richest natural resources in the world. China, the second-largest economy, has taken a leading position in international relations and acted as a regional and world economic leader. By developing political influence through economic projects, China is pushing world leaders out of traditional spheres of influence and filling them with their political presence. Africa is an example of China's political presence in its long-term foreign policy strategy. In particular, East Africa has become a priority for international cooperation. This strategy has long gone beyond regional influence and is dedicated to building a new world order, where China plays the role of a great economic power. In this regard, the study of the following aspects and questions is of the greatest interest: Why is there a mutual interest in the presence of China in Africa, what is the model of this presence, and what difficulties arise for the free implementation of foreign policy goals in Africa? The author also aims to explain specific reasons driving China's engagement in regional investment, and focuses on specifics of China-African foreign policy.

Keywords: China - Africa Relations, China -Africa investment, Soft Power, Sino-Africa Relations

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Introduction

Sino-Africa Relations

The first diplomatic Sino-African relations began in 1950 under Mao Zedong when the first bilateral agreements with African countries were signed. During this period, one of the important mechanisms for China's cooperation with African countries appeared—the program of economic assistance to developing countries after official visits of Prime Minister Zhou Enlai to African states. The visits by Prime Minister Zhou Enlai coincided with the decolonization of African countries. At that time, Premier Zhou Enlai entered formal diplomatic relations between Beijing and African countries. The delegation of over 50 diplomats led by Chinese Foreign Minister Chen Yi toured Africa [26]. As a result, the delegation visited Egypt, Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Ghana, Mali, Guinea, Sudan, Ethiopia, and Somalia [2]. He then promised to allocate over \$500 million to Egypt, Tanzania, Algeria, Ghana, Guinea, the Republic of Congo, and Mali. The main message of this visit was to support African countries in the post-colonial period and fight imperialism. Thus, the first diplomatic relations were established with Egypt in 1956[24]. China initiated conferences in Africa. In 1954, the Geneva Conference in Indochina, Afro-Asian Conference in Bandung Indonesia in 1955 [22], and Afro-Asian Conference in Algeria in 1965. Most African countries that supported China on the Taiwan issue strengthened these formal

diplomatic relations, which laid the foundation for China's economic initiatives in Africa. In the 1970s, development grants increased, and the list of recipient countries expanded significantly to include Tunisia, Burundi, Mauritius, Rwanda, Sierra Leone, Togo, Cameroon, Zaire, the Malagasy Republic, and Chad. By the end of the decade, China had promised to pay more than \$2 billion to thirty-two countries on the continent. The mechanism of the economic assistance program varied from that adopted at the time on the continent. With its help, China was able to expand its sales markets due to the cost of building facilities for which China supplied equipment and competent specialists had to be paid by income from the sale of goods imported from China. The terms for issuing loans varied from 10 to 40 years, and it was possible to repay them in foreign currency or in goods sent for exports.

With investment in infrastructure, construction, energy, transportation, and other fields, significant contributions have been made to education through scholarships for African students every year to study in China.

Deng Xiaoping continued to develop these relations through the economic initiatives of the New China, China Open Door Policy, opening China to international trade and investment[**Error! Reference source not found.**]. In 1992, Deng Xiaoping said firmly, “We would come to a dead end should we fail to adhere to socialism, reform and opening up, develop the economy, and improve people’s livelihood, and the fundamental policies must be maintained for 100 years, unswervingly[**Error! Reference source not found.**].”

The Industrial Age expanded China's trade with African countries. Xi Jinping once again confirmed China's long-term intentions in Africa at the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation Summit in 2018[**Error! Reference source not found.**], announcing the priorities for the following years:

- industry promotion,
- assistance to agriculture through participation in China International Import Expo and infrastructure through investment construction or other models,
- financial assistance projects in the field of green development, ecology and environmental protection,
- government scholarships for students from Africa,
- modernize several health and medical care programs for Africa,
- cultural exchange through the Institute of African Studies,
- investments in healthcare,
- China-Africa Peace and Security Fund to provide security and support for the UN mission¹.

Thus, China is rapidly developing bilateral relations with the countries of the African continent, based on the interest in natural resources in exchange for investment in the infrastructure that African countries need. China's relations with Africa are conducted through diplomacy, trade, and investment, which is an important component of bilateral diplomatic relations.

Africa in Chinese Foreign Policy

China followed the model of a (one-center) superpower and several great powers. However, the rapidly changing political environment requires China to make quick policy adjustments, in which it continues to maintain established ties with neighboring countries and countries in the African region. Political and economic relations with actors are built on the basis of the interests of the parties. With a clear strategy, definite goals, and concrete actions, China opens up prospects not only for itself but also for other players.

Interest in Africa is dictated by the need for energy, metals, and minerals to support the ever-growing economy of China. The need for resources is offset by the contact with countries with large reserves of natural resources. China's closest neighbors and

¹ For full details on three years eight major initiatives with African countries in the next three years and beyond, covering fields such as industrial promotion, infrastructure connectivity, trade facilitation, and green development, Liangyu, “Xi Jinping Says China to Implement Eight Major Initiatives with African Countries,” <https://www.xinhuanet.com>, September 3, 2018.

countries in other regions cover China's needs for raw materials and receive economic contracts that develop the economies of these countries in return. The rational policy, based on satisfying its own interests and needs in the most beneficial ways, led China to East Africa, rich in oil and minerals, where it strengthened its position. The key point in these relations is the security of trade sea routes in the Indian Ocean and South China Sea. This path also leads to the Persian Gulf being the richest region in hydrocarbons. The zone of Chinese influence, which is being formed in Eurasia and Africa, is constantly growing, not in a superficial, purely quantitative sense, but in a deeper one, corresponding to the era of globalization.

China's geographical location contributes to the successful spread of Chinese influence in these regions. The expansion of influence from Central Asia to the South China Sea and from the Russian Far East to the Indian Ocean has turned China into a powerful continental power. Investments positively affect the development of export and import GDP quotas. For example, the first increased from 27% in 1990 to 35% in 2000, and from 25% in 1990 to 31% in 2003[**Error! Reference source not found.**]. However, some authors say that all African states remain raw material appendages of developed countries because they cannot invest in promising sectors of the economy [**Error! Reference source not found.**].

African countries remain important objects of economic cooperation and a rich source of raw materials for the economies of America, Europe, China, India, and Russia. Coffee, tea, cocoa, tropical fruits, and spices are in demand everywhere. It contains phenomenal mineral reserves. "The Black Continent ranks first in the world in terms of reserves of manganese, chromium, bauxite, gold, platinum, cobalt, vanadium, diamonds, phosphorus, fluorite, second in terms of reserves of copper, asbestos, uranium, antimony, beryllium, graphite, third in terms of reserves of oil, gas, mercury, iron; there are also large reserves of ores of titanium, nickel, bismuth, lithium, tantalum, niobium, tin, tungsten and precious stones. The richest deposits of diamonds in Africa (South Africa, Zimbabwe) and gold (South Africa, Ghana, Mali, Republic of the Congo) are also of interest for investment. Nigeria and Algeria have large oil fields. Bauxites were mined in Guinea and Ghana. The resources of phosphorites, manganese, iron, and lead-zinc ores are concentrated in the northern coast of Africa" [**Error! Reference source not found.**].

Libya, Algeria, Nigeria, Angola, Gabon, and other countries export oil and show high rates of economic growth. Taken together, these countries are of great interest to the world's main actors because of the huge reserves of minerals, which have not been fully explored. Therefore, an extensive pool of investments, particularly from China, is concentrated in this region. Chinese pragmatism in foreign economic policy makes Africa a priority area for Chinese investment. For example, in 2004, China invested in Angola's road program in exchange for a share of its large oil reserves. From 2009 to 2012, the flow of direct investment from China to Africa increased from \$1.44 billion to \$2.52 billion, with an annual growth of 20.5%. In total, from 2001 to 2018, investments in African countries amounted to \$41 billion[**Error! Reference source not found.**]. At present, more than 2,000 Chinese enterprises operate in more than 50 African countries and regions, with private enterprises accounting for most of them. Since 2000, China's investment in Africa has entered a rapid development phase, with government support. Most Western analysts believe that the main driver of China's investment in Africa is access to resources, and is thus focused on a few resource-rich countries. Chinese investment is actually received by 49 African countries, and their share of coverage is about 83 percent. These figures also exceed the investments of other powers in Africa, such as the US, the EU, India, Brazil, Turkey, and South Korea. For example, in 2010, the top 10 invested countries are: South Africa (31.8%), Nigeria (9.3%), Zambia (7.2%), Algeria (7.2%), Democratic Republic of the Congo (4.8%), Sudan (4.7%), Niger (2.9%), Ethiopia (2.8%), Angola (2.7%) and Egypt (2.6%). These countries receive 76% of all Chinese investment in Africa.

Of the member countries of the East African Community, Tanzania remains one of the largest recipients of Chinese investment. China is investing in Tanzania's coal mining sector(the 2011 investment was \$3 billion). Among the investors are large companies such as the China Machine-Building International Corporation (power industry), China Civil Engineering Construction Corporation (construction works), and China Henan International Cooperation Group of Companies Limited (road construction, water supply, etc.). 3/4 of foreign construction firms operating in the country are Chinese [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. In Kenya, a 50-kilometer section of the eight-lane Thika Superhighway was built with Chinese investment. The largest share of Chinese investment in Africa was in the construction and mining sectors. The Democratic Republic of Congo, Zambia, Zimbabwe,

Tanzania, Mozambique, and Nigeria top the list of recipients of extractive industry investments. Among these, two countries were located in East Africa.

Manufacturing is China's key investment field in Africa. From 2009 to 2012, the volume of investment by Chinese enterprises in the manufacturing sector in Africa amounted to \$ 1.33 billion. By 2020, foreign direct investment (FDI) in the manufacturing sector amounted to \$ 6.13 billion [**Error! Reference source not found.**].

China is investing in manufacturing in countries that have limited resources. Investments in sugar mills in Mali, glass and fur processors, automobile factories in Ethiopia, Uganda, textiles, and steel pipe projects [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. The East African region is particularly attractive to China because of its oil factors. Notably, it predicts that China's oil consumption will exceed that of the US as early as 2034. Therefore, China requires new sources of energy. Considering global oil flows, East Africa ranked second, after the Middle East, among Chinese oil suppliers. China's great interest lies in the significant oil deposits discovered in Uganda, Kenya, and South Sudan.

Hydrocarbons are not the only African raw material China requires. Ores and metals are also of interest, such as zinc, cobalt, copper, uranium, and bauxite, which are imported mainly from Zimbabwe among the countries of East Africa [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. Diverse cooperative mechanisms with African countries, high-level official visits, and support for various economic projects in the region have strengthened China's position in Africa. China has been able to convince African leaders of its friendly intentions by allocating funds for the development of countries as well as through the creation of a Development Fund and holding Cooperation Forums [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. Moreover, China issues loans to African countries in favorable terms, invests in the African economy, and writes off debts to the poorest countries, such as cash flow stimulating African countries to enter into various commercial contracts with China. Given these political and economic factors, Africa is one of the most important regions in China's political and economic security strategy, to which China skillfully connects diplomatic channels, investing huge economic power in Africa, which receives half of China's total investment in Africa, where Africa is the second largest region in terms of Chinese FDI. Large reserves of minerals, including oil, in East Africa, which is second among other regions of Africa in terms of oil imports for China. The line of diplomatic cooperation at the highest level, at the level of high-ranking officials, considering the programs of economic forums and cooperation, allows China to guide East African leaders and, accordingly, countries on a development program that triples the CCP. Therefore, we conclude that there is a large share of China's political presence in Africa.

Currently, China is striving to maximize its involvement in the international process of globalization. This is due not only to economic necessity, but also to the political role of China in the modern world as one of the key actors in the international division of labor and a political regional partner. Therefore, China is not only a necessary element of international relations, but also a global threat, which gives it the right to change its global positioning. Moreover, not only are there economic ties in the wake of China's policy, but there is also cooperation in the fields of security and culture.

Evolution of China and East Africa relations

China's geographical position, as well as elements of a developed Western economy and centralized management, are China's advantages in international relations. Therefore, China came to the shores of East Africa even before our era and again returned to the shores of the Indian Ocean in Africa with the end of the era of colonial rule, where it created competition with other important actors in international economic relations.

It is in East Africa where China's acquaintance with the entire continent begins. Thus far, China has established diplomatic relations with 51 out of 55 countries on the continent, the latest of which was South Sudan in 2011, reaching a consensus on major international issues, identifying common interests, and expressing their willingness to deepen cooperation. Frequent high-level reciprocal visits have promoted mutual understanding and trust, and have effectively improved the development of bilateral ties [**Error! Reference source not found.**].

In the past six decades, China's relations with East Africa have gone through three phases of development in China-Africa relations[**Error! Reference source not found.**].

The first stage occurred in the early 1950s. until the late 1970s, included a program of economic assistance to developing countries. During this period, both China and Africa focused on political development because of their newfound independence. The purpose of these bilateral relations was mutual political support in the fight against colonialism and imperialism. One of the most effective mechanisms for establishing China's economic ties with African countries has become regular high-level visits in which Chinese politicians promote the idea of opposing China and Africa to the West. At first, such visits were purely declarative in nature, reinforcing the anti-colonial sentiments of Africans, but at the moment, China had already prepared the moral and emotional ground, signing some of the most expensive contracts with the countries of the continent as part of high-level visits. These initiatives led to an increase in China's trade with African countries, and mainly due to commodity credits, the volume of trade increased from \$12 million in 1950 to \$34.74 million in 1955 and to \$250 million in 1965 [**Error! Reference source not found.**].

In the 1970s, there was a noticeable boost and an increase of up to 30% in the mutual trade between China and African countries, such as Tanzania, Zambia, Nigeria, Egypt, Morocco, and Sudan. In the late 1970s, China-Africa trade grew at an average annual rate of 3.6 percent. China imported more minerals, such as phosphates and copper, as well as raw materials and agricultural products, such as cotton, timber, bananas, and coffee, while Africa imported consumer goods, equipment, and foodstuffs, such as rice, tea, canned meat, and fish[**Error! Reference source not found.**].

The second stage occurred during the 1980s. After adopting a policy of opening up and reforming in the late 1970s, China developed into an industrialized country. China continues to attach significant importance to Africa. For example, Chinese premier Zhao Ziyang launched a series of diplomatic initiatives in December 1982 in 11 African countries, promoting the "four principles" of Chinese cooperation with Africa: equality and mutual benefit, emphasis on practical results, diversification, and economic development [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. In the first decade of reform and opening-up (1978-1988), the share of African countries in China's foreign trade dropped significantly. The reason for this phenomenon was the intensification and dynamic growth of China's economic ties with developed countries, as well as Hong Kong and Macau, as a result of attracting direct investment from there. By the beginning of the 90s African countries had accounted for less than 2% of China's foreign trade, similar to other Asian countries [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. However, in absolute terms, trade increases. In 1990, China's exports to African countries amounted to slightly less than \$1.2 billion, while imports exceeded \$0.3 billion - against \$0.5 billion and \$0.2 billion, respectively, in 1980.

The third stage embraces the 90s. During this period, China invested \$51.19 million in 102 projects in African countries. The total volume of exports and imports increased by more than 40% [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. The situation began to change fundamentally from the end of the 20th century, when a new superpower, China, emerged on the geopolitical horizon. The collapse of the USSR in 1991 led to the formation of a geopolitical vacuum, which of course could not last long enough - other players appeared in African affairs, among which China took the place of the USSR. The situation began to change even more dynamically in the first decade of the 21st century [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. By the end of the 90s China's trade with African countries had grown in both absolute and relative terms. In 1999, exports to the continent amounted to \$4.1 billion, imports - \$2.4 billion. African countries accounted for 2.1% of Chinese exports and 1.4% of imports[**Error! Reference source not found.**].

A new phase began in 2000 with the establishment of the China-Africa Cooperation Forum (FOCAC) at ministerial conferences. The first conference was held in Beijing, where the Beijing Declaration and the China-Africa Cooperation Program were adopted, it touched upon aspects of social and economic development, where China assumed obligations to increase assistance to the countries of the continent, and almost all the obligations assumed by China in the Beijing Declaration have already been fulfilled [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. The FOCAC is the most important platform for advancing interest in Africa. FOCAC brings together 51 states with diplomatic relations with China. Since its inception, FOCAC has gradually become an important platform for collective dialogue and an effective mechanism for strengthening the practical cooperation between China and African countries.

Risks and Opportunity for Chinese Investment in Africa

China's lending data from 2000 to 2019 show that credit inflows are diversifying by reducing funding for countries with a less developed industrial sector, even those with natural resources. From 2010 to 2017, of the \$117 billion allocated by China to African countries, the countries with the least developed industries (Madagascar, Niger, Liberia, Burundi and the Central African Republic) received \$868 million, and some (Gambia and Burkina Faso) did not receive loans at all. In countries with low gross national income (GNI), loan requests are rejected [Error! Reference source not found.]. China finances, to a greater extent, the strong economies of Africa such as Angola, Kenya, and Nigeria. As mentioned, this reduces lending. China has also invested in the fast-growing markets of Mozambique, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Ghana, and Ethiopia.

African countries are attracted to accelerated procedures for processing loans. According to the former president of Senegal, obtaining approval from Chinese authorities takes only a few months. China avoids intervening in the internal affairs of the countries it lends, but most loans are made under tenders in which Chinese companies participate. For example, a Chinese investment of \$771 million allocated for the construction of the Bui Dam was spent on the Chinese company Sinohydro, which built the dam [Error! Reference source not found.]. Thus, in contrast to the 90s, when Sino-African relations were political, ideological, or diplomatic, since the beginning of the century, China has been exclusively building political and economic relations with African countries [Error! Reference source not found.].

The growth of the Chinese economy, which requires natural resources, minerals, and oil, has shaped the direction of the political strategy in Africa. By investing in various sectors of African countries, China, whose economy depends on resources, requires investment security [Error! Reference source not found.].

As practice shows, China's strategy to diversify risks has proven effective. Remaining an undemanding investor, China invests only in steadily developing African countries that are rich in resources that the Chinese economy needs. Gradually increasing official development assistance in African countries has solved its foreign policy interests [Error! Reference source not found.].

Therefore, investments in new oil-producing countries diversify risk diversification [Error! Reference source not found.]. According to the China - Africa Research Initiative (CARI), African countries received \$143 billion in loans from China from 2000 to 2017 (2018 research)[Error! Reference source not found.]. However, this strategy is not effective in any country. Kenya's debt to China exceeded its GDP by 62% as of March 2018 [Error! Reference source not found.], the same situation as Angola[Error! Reference source not found.].

Perspectives

International relations between China and African countries are based on the principles of equality, mutual benefits, and joint development in trade and economic cooperation with Africa. There have been many bilateral visits by Chinese President Xi Jinping and African heads of state. The African market has become a priority in foreign economic relations with continents rich in natural and human resources. Beijing encourages Chinese investors to increase interaction with African countries, "to help Africa create more jobs, increase tax revenues for the budgets of African countries, bring high technology to East Africa and share business management experience." Africa has become the 4th largest recipient of Chinese investment worldwide [Error! Reference source not found.].

Energy resources, oil, iron ore, timber, and copper are a partial list of the primary products purchased by China from Africa. In addition, China is increasing its imports of finished industrial products, and Chinese enterprises are engaged in agriculture, mining, and construction, as well as in the areas of deep processing, engineering, finance, trade, real estate, and tourism. China pays special attention to the manufacturing industry when creating jobs [Error! Reference source not found.].

A separate direction for China in Africa is the export of Chinese products to African countries. Cheap Chinese products are in demand in Africa, and, along with China's policy of non-intervention, economic contacts between the parties are generally developing successfully. problems remained in this area. Therefore, China is building trade and economic ties and leveling the negative circumstances that hinder this process. However, if China took risks earlier by investing in an unstable and not rich region, it has finally paid attention to the need for a balanced approach and a thorough analysis of all associated political and economic risks [Error! Reference source not found.] .

The insufficient experience of Chinese companies hinders the growth of trade and economic cooperation between parties, and despite the fact that the number of cooperation projects is growing rapidly, their quality is improving slightly [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. The potential of the continent requires improvement in bilateral relationships. Issues such as labor protection for the extraction of facilities and increasing personnel policy [**Error! Reference source not found.**]. In order to eliminate the difficulties in the development of Sino-African relations, Beijing is making a "soft-power" attempt to find a common ideological base in the light of the new concept of the "Chinese dream." This became another new moment in the dialogue between parties. According to Xi Jinping, "China and Africa are closely united not only by strong traditional friendships and common interests, but also by separate dreams. Today, as economic integration continues to strengthen, the Chinese Dream of Prosperity, the African Dream of Development, and the World Dream of Communicating and Winning are closely intertwined to promote common progress"[**Error! Reference source not found.**].

Thus, the success of Chinese economic and political activities in Africa is based on political conditions for the implementation of Chinese investment, trade, and financial assistance. Therefore, China will continue its soft power policy to maintain its position and access to natural resources, which are necessary for the Chinese economy.

The above once again confirms that the "soft power" used by China, coupled with the colossal economic potential, outweighs all other - environmental, social, political - considerations. This makes the prospects for a Chinese presence in East Africa extremely broad. The flexibility of China's leaders' political positions makes it possible for the country to cooperate with a diverse range of political regimes and meet the interests of the state. Various negative effects from the presence of a country in the region (deterioration of the environment, depletion of the natural resources of African states, corruption, limited participation of citizens of countries in production, etc.) can limit the topics and extent of China's influence in the region, creating political and economic risks. Since Africa is increasingly becoming an important part of the strategy of every industrialized country that needs natural resources to strengthen its own position in the world as well as to solve domestic problems, we can therefore assume that China needs to adapt to the rapidly changing conditions for conducting foreign policy in African countries to achieve medium- and long-term prospects in the region.

Conclusion

In recent years, China has become the first trading partner of African countries, overtaking the United States as well as the largest creditor of the states of the region, displacing the World Bank from this position. The standard of living for the population is increasing. It also promises good prospects for trade development with Africa, primarily in terms of the supply of consumer goods. The discovery of new oil fields makes the region even more attractive for investment purposes.

There is no doubt that China, by cooperating with African countries in the economic sphere, opens up new opportunities for Africa to grow its economy and infrastructure and actually demonstrates to the countries of the continent the advantages of China's socio-economic development model, which is undoubtedly beneficial for China, which has access to rich regions of minerals that can cover the needs of the Chinese economy. Therefore, China is developing political and economic relations in this region based on the policy of soft power and non-intervention, as well as diversifying risks and adjusting to the constantly changing situation both globally and in this region.

Thus, China's constant investment in African countries positively influences political diplomatic relations with African countries accompanied by economic growth, and gives China an advantage in the continent as one of the largest investors in African countries. Investing in infrastructure to optimize export-import flows between China and Africa in exchange for natural resources makes Africa even more attractive to China.

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References

- [1] Abdi Latif Dahir, "Taiwan Now Has One Diplomatic Ally Left in Africa," Quartz Africa Weekly Brief, May 28, 2018, pp. 28–32.
- [2] Abegunrin, O., & Manyeruke, C. (2020). *China's Power in Africa*. Springer International Publishing., <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-3-030-21994-9.pdf> , Accessed: November 2022.
- [3] Abramova I.O., Morozenskaya E.V., *African economy in the context of market transformations*. M., 2010., p. 26
- [4] Kieh G.K., jr. , *Africa and the new globalization*. , Aldershot; Burlington (VJ): Ashgate, 2008. – XIII, 192 p.
- [5] Adegoke, Yinka. 2018. "Chinese Debt Doesn't Have to be a Problem for African Countries." Available at <https://qz.com/africa/1276710/china-in-africa-chinese-debt-news-better-management-by-african-leaders/>, Accessed October 2, 2022.
- [6] Alden, C., Alao, A., Chun, Z., & Barber, L. (Eds.). (2017). *China and Africa: Building peace and security cooperation on the continent*. Springer.
- [7] Alves, Ana C. 2011. "China's Oil Diplomacy: Comparing Chinese Economic Statecraft in Angola and Brazil." PhD thesis, The London School of Economics and Political Science.
- [8] Africa sees future ties with China through CPPCC [Electronic resource]. – Access: <http://english.cntv.cn/program/china24/20140303/105947.shtml> , Accessed March 31,2022.
- [9] Brandon Locke, Brussels International Center, <https://www.bic-rhr.com/research/chinese-engagement-africa-understanding-risks-and-opportunities-european-union> , Accessed November 13, 2022.
- [10] Chinese Economic Engagement in Africa: Implications for U.S. Policy , <https://www.fpri.org/article/2022/01/chinese-economic-engagement-in-africa/>
- [11] Deutsch T. L., Usov V. A. - Tanzania. "Rising" Asian Powers Explore East Africa // *Asia and Africa Today*, No. 12, December 2014, pp. 21-26.
- [12] Dyushebaev A., "China's interests in Africa", *Time of the East* , <http://www.easttime.ru/analyt> , Access:ed : May 11, 2022.
- [13] Deborah Brautigam, Xinshen Diao (2017). *Chinese Investment in Africa: How Much do we Know?* , https://pedl.cepr.org/sites/default/files/PEDL_Synthesis_Papers_Piece_No._2.pdf , Accessed: January 19, 2023
- [14] Dreher, Axel, Andreas Fuchs, Brad Parks, Austin M. Strange, and Michael J. Tierney. 2018. "Apples and Dragon Fruits: The Determinants of Aid and other Forms of State Financing from China to Africa." *International Studies Quarterly* 62 (1): 182–194. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqx052>, Accessed November 13, 2022.
- [15] Dahir, Abdi L. 2018a. "China Now Owns More Than 70% of Kenya's Bilateral Debt." Quartz Africa. Available at <https://qz.com/africa/1324618/china-is-kenyas-largest-creditor-with-72-of-total-bilateral-debt/> , Accessed November 2, 2022.
- [16] Filippov V. - Colonialism: the second coming. – RIAC - July 23, 2012, http://russiancouncil.ru/inner/?id_4=633#top , Accessed : January 19, 2023
- [17] Grinyaev S., Arutyunyan G., "Egypt is a mirror of the "great game" in Africa", *Commercial and industrial statements - Edition of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Russian Federation*, <http://www.tpp-inform.ru/global/939.html>, Accessed November 13, 2022.
- [18] Jones, L. A. (2018). Can communities close to Bui National Park mediate the impacts of Bui Dam construction? An exploration of the views of some selected households. *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation*, 10(1), 12-38.

- [19] Konings, Piet. 2007. "China and Africa: Building a Strategic Partnership." *Journal of Developing Societies* 23 (3): 341–367. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0169796X0702300303>, Accessed November 13, 2022.
- [20] Liu Qinghai, "Realities and Opportunities – Chinese Private Enterprises in Africa", Institute of African Studies at Zhejiang Normal University(IASZNU), <http://ias.zjnu.cn/en/show.php?id=3632> , Accessed: 12.18.2022.
- [21] Li Lanqing, op. cit., pp. 426–427.
- [22] Liangyu, "Xi Jinping Says China to Implement Eight Major Initiatives with African Countries," <https://www.xinhuanet.com>, September 3, 2018.
- [23] Marilyn Young, *The Vietnam Wars: 1945–1990*, New York: Harper Perennial, 1991, p. 41. "Indochina- Midway in the Geneva Conference: Address by the Secretary of State," Avalon Project, Yale Law School, May 7, 1954. Also see Bruce Larkin, *China and Africa, 1949–1970: The Foreign Policy of the People's Republic of China*, Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 1971
- [24] Petrov N., Geveling L. V., "Africa in Questions and Answers", *Asia and Africa Today*, No. 10, October 2010, pp. 9-13
- [25] Victorien A. Mechanisms of Chinese expansion into Africa.// *Bulletin of RUDN University, International Relations series*, 2014, No. 1
- [26] Zhang Chun, "The Sino-Africa Relationship: Toward a New Strategic Partnership", The London School of Economics and Political Science, <http://www.lse.ac.uk/IDEAS/publications/reports/pdf/SR016/SR-016-Chun.pdf>, Accessed: 12.18.2022.
- [27] "Zhou Enlai's African Safari," www.blackpast.org. Retrieved July 24, 2018.
- [28] Abegunrin, O., & Manyeruke, C. (2020). *China's Power in Africa*. Springer International Publishing. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/978-3-030-21994-9.pdf> , Accessed: 12.18.2022.
- [29]<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1259624/chinese-fdi-stock-to-africa-in-manufacturing-sector/#statisticContainer> , Published Saifaddin Galal Nov 16, 2022
- [30] "Data: Chinese Loans and Aid to Africa.", Available at www.sais-cari.org/data-chinese-loans-and-aid-to-africa/ , Accessed November 1, 2022.
- [31] China in the heart of Africa, <http://www.un.org/africarenewal/magazine/january-2013/china-heart-africa> , Accessed March 31,2022.
- China and Africa to resolve problems in good faith [Electronic resource]. – Access: <http://english.cntv.cn/program/new-update/20130409/105347.shtml> , Accessed March 31,2022.
- [33] China in the heart of Africa [Electronic resource]. – Access: <http://www.un.org/africarenewal/magazine/january-2013/china-heart-africa> , Accessed March 31,2022.
- [34] Deputy Foreign Minister of China: "China and Africa should make efforts to develop China-Africa relations", <http://russian.cri.cn/841/2013/03/18/1s461351.htm>, Accessed March 31,2022.
- [35] Forum on China-Africa Cooperation - China's African Policy- Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) - 2006, <http://www.focac.com> , Accessed: 11.21.2022.
- [36] Forum on China-Africa Cooperation - China's African Policy- Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) - 2006, <http://www.focac.org/eng/zt/zgdfzccwj/t230479>, Accessed November 13, 2022.
- [37] Geo-politics, China and Africa, http://www.chinainafrica.co.uk/china_geo_politics.html , Accessed March 31,2022.
- [38] International Energy Outlook 2014 - U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), September 2014 , [http://www.eia.gov/forecasts/ieo/pdf/0484\(2014\).pdf](http://www.eia.gov/forecasts/ieo/pdf/0484(2014).pdf) , Access:ed : May 31, 2022.
- [39] Were, Anzette., "Debt Trap? Chinese Loans and Africa's Development Options." , South African Institute of International Affairs (SAIIA)-Policy Insights 66, 2018.

